

Patterns and effects of elite scientists' university-industry research collaboration in China

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Abstract

In the age of the knowledge economy, “university-industry” research collaboration (UIRC) has emerged as a significant strategy for fostering cross-sectoral collaborative innovation across the world. However, little is known about what the current state of UIRC is, and how UIRC affects the individual scientists' academic performance in China. This study empirically investigates the UIRC status of 679 elite scientists in China across six scientific fields, including chemistry, physics, mathematics, computer science and engineering, materials science and engineering, and mechanical science and engineering, during 1999-2017 by bibliometric methods. The results show that the UIRC of Chinese elite scientists has certain patterns in terms of discipline, gender, and collaborate enterprises. According to bibliometric measures, scientists who participated in UIRC generally have better academic performance, as evidenced by their higher number of publications, more collaborators, and extended periods of high-quality research outputs.

Introduction

Scientists, as the primary producers of knowledge, have been recognized for their significance to the innovation and development of the economy (Etzkowitz, 1993; Nelson, 2004). However, there is ongoing debate over the effects of direct scientific research collaboration between academics and industry. On one hand, practice and research have increasingly demonstrated that collaboration between academics and industry not only fosters applied innovation but also encourages and advances basic research, and that academics who are adept at commercialization also outperform their peers in scientific research (Etzkowitz, 1996; Azoulay, Ding & Stuart, 2007; Barra, Maietta & Zotti, 2019). On the other hand, the “disinterested” nature of science and the long-term objectives of research, however, may be compromised by the increasing participation of academics with enterprises, according to certain research (Biscotti D, et al. 2012; Holloway, 2015). To resolve this argument, researchers have conducted a number of empirical studies based on various country experiences. In the U.S., researchers who received industry funding published more papers and filed patents more frequently than those who did not, engaged in more administrative and professional activities, and earned more money,

according to a survey conducted by Blumenthal et al. (1986) of more than 1,200 biotechnology researchers at 40 major U.S. universities. Powell & Owen-Smith (1998) discovered that non-academic institutions, particularly researchers in businesses, have generated the most and most significant articles and publications in the subject of biotechnology (measured by the average citations in 1988-1992). Haeussler & Colyvas's research (2011) reveals that elite scientists are more likely to engage in academic commercialization activities than the others in UK and Germany.

To sum up, despite ongoing controversy, the global trend of scientists engaging in UIRC is unstoppable. It is of enormous theoretical and practical importance to understand the situation and trend of scientists' participation in UIRC at individual level, and to reveal the effect of how participating in UIRC affect their academic performance. Our goal in this study, therefore, is to (1) explore the status and pattern of Chinese elite scientists' participation in UIRC, and (2) examine the spillover effect of what UIRC have on the scientific community and scientists themselves, by using a variety of bibliometric metrics, including publications, citations, h-index, collaborators, etc.

Data and Methods

In this study, we select six scientific fields – chemistry, physics, mathematics, computer science and engineering, materials science and engineering, and mechanical science and engineering – as the research subjects, then we collected who were elected as “Changjiang Scholars” in these six fields from 1999 to 2017 (between the initial year and the last year of opening to the public), along with their personal information as gender, age, working institutions, etc. The “Chang Jiang Scholars Program”, co-founded by the Li Ka Shing Foundation and the Chinese Ministry of Education, has been active since 1998, and has become a flagship program for attracting and rewarding the top scientists in China's top universities (Li et al.).

Regarding the method used to collect the scientist samples, in detail, we first gathered the employment statuses and academic specialties of the Changjiang Scholars, after which we used manual matching to identify the fields to which the Changjiang Scholars belonged and subsequently classified each

Changjiang Scholars into specific fields. By doing so, a total of 679 samples of scientists were collected, including 185 from the fields of chemistry, 122 from physics, 71 from mathematics, 47 from computer science and engineering, 157 from the fields of material science and engineering, and 97 from mechanical science and engineering. Figure 1 displays the distribution of number of Changjiang scholars over time.

Figure 1. The number of "Changjiang Scholars" across different scientific fields over time (Changjiang Scholars were not awarded in 2013 but were supplemented in 2014).

By preparing bibliometric analysis, we use the Scopus database to query the publication data and bibliometric index data of each Changjiang scholar between the year of 2011 and 2020, including the author information, affiliated institutions, publication date, etc. Then we detect the affiliation information of all the publications to identify whether a scientist has participated in UIRC. Thus, depending on whether a scientist participated in UIRC from 2011 to 2020, we can divide them into two categories: UIRC group and None-UIRC group. For accessing the academic impact of UIRC on the scientists, we select number of publications, h-index, number of citations, number of collaborators as the bibliometric indicators. Finally, we compare the academic performance of two groups of scientists using independent sample t-test and Cohen's coefficient, which we base on the concept of Coarsened Exact Matching.

Results I: The UIRC Patterns of Changjiang Scholars

Subjects

A total of 416 scientists, or roughly 61% of the sampled Changjiang Scholars in this study, have published at least one UIRC paper between 2011 and 2020, which is a reasonably high level. Among them, less than half of the Changjiang scholars in the field of mathematics were involved in UIRC research,

compared to 94% of scientists who participated in UIRC in the field of computer science and engineering, followed by 76% in the field of materials science and engineering, 69% in the field of mechanical science and engineering, 59% in the field of chemistry, and 57% in the field of physics (see Figure 2). It is evident that there are clear disciplinary differences in the level of scientists' participation in UIRC research activities: generally, scientists in engineering sciences are more inclined to participate in UIRC, while scientists in basic sciences are relatively lower.

Figure 2. The number and distribution of Changjiang Scholars participating in UIRC across different subjects.

Gender

Approximately 72% of the 39 female scientists sampled for this study have engaged in UIRC, which is higher than the 61% for the sample of male scientists. There is a limitation of insufficient observation samples since there are very few female scientists (less than 6%) among all Changjiang Scholars sampled in this study, and even just one in the subject of mathematics.

Collaborative enterprises

The majority of high-frequency collaborative enterprises are large state-owned enterprises of China. Among them, China's large state-owned enterprises SINOPEC and China Electronics Technology Group Corporation have the highest frequency of UIRC publications in the fields of chemistry, and materials science and engineering, respectively; China Electronics Technology Group Corporation has the highest frequency of UIRC activities in mathematics; Alibaba Group Holding Ltd. wins in physics; Microsoft and British Petroleum Company (BP plc) are the most frequently UIRC international enterprises that Changjiang Scholars collaborate with in the fields of computer science and engineering, and mechanical science and engineering. Table 1 lists the top 10 collaborative enterprises in terms of the frequency of UIRC publications.

Table 1. The top 10 collaborative enterprises in terms of the frequency of UIRC publications.

Rank	Chemistry	Physics	Math	Computer Sci. & Eng.	Materials Sci. & Eng.	Mechanical Sci. & Eng.
1	SINOPEC	Alibaba Group Holding Ltd.	China Electronics Technology Group Corporation	Microsoft	SINOPEC	BP plc
2	China National Petroleum Corporation	Aerospace Corporation	Novo Nordisk A/S	Alibaba Group Holding Ltd.	China National Petroleum Corporation	General Motors
3	State Grid Corporation of China	China National Nuclear Corporation	Chevron Corporation	Tencent	Shanghai Baosteel Research Institute	Siemens
4	Guangdong Power Grid Corporation	China Electronics Technology Group Corporation	ExxonMobil	Huawei Technologies Co., Ltd.	China National Nuclear Corporation	ABB Group
5	Synfaels China Co., Ltd.	IBM	General Electric	Intel	Samsung	Commercial Aircraft Corporation of China
6	ENN Group Co., Ltd.	Intel	Merck	IBM	Tata Steel Europe Ltd.	SAIC
7	JEOL Ltd.	Microsoft	Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc.	State Grid Corporation of China	SINTEF	Unilever
8	GlaxoSmithKline	Roche Co. Ltd	Baidu Inc	Alphabet Inc.	Aero Engine Corporation of China	China Aerodynamics Research and Development Center
9	Huntsman International LLC	Volkswagen AG	/	Baidu Inc	Kenametal, Inc.	FAW Group Corporation
10	BASF	FAW Group Corporation	/	Hewlett-Packard	FAW Group Corporation	State Grid Corporation of China

Additionally, scientists in different fields have varying preferences for global UIRC. Scientists in the three disciplines of chemistry, materials science and engineering, and mechanical science and engineering are relatively more willing to collaborate with domestic enterprises, scientists in physics, mathematics, and computer science and engineering are relatively more willing to collaborate with international enterprises, with the international UIRC proportion of 68%, 62.5%, and 56.5%, respectively; while scientists in the three disciplines of chemistry, materials science and engineering, and mechanical science and engineering are relatively more willing to cooperate with domestic enterprises, and their international UIRC proportion for less than half.

Results II: The Impact of UIRC on Changjiang Scholars' Academic Performance

Productivity

Overall, involvement in UIRC has a very favorable effect on the scientific outputs of Changjiang Scholars. Scientists who took part in UIRC published an average of 401.6 publications, compared to 246.5 publications for scientists who did not take part (t-test, $p < 0.0001$). By investigating the variations among subjects, we found that except for chemistry and mathematics, the UIRC group scientists publish on average of more publications in general than None-UIRC group scientists, and these differences are statistically significant (t-test, $p < 0.0001$).

Research impact

In terms of research impact, this study mainly investigated the differences between the two groups of scientists through two bibliometric indicators: the number of citations per publication and h index of scientists. The number of publications referenced generally does not change significantly between the two groups of scientists (29.43 vs. 30.48), but there

is a significant difference in the mean value of the h index (49.00 vs. 40.53, $p < 0.0001$). These findings suggest that, over time, the output of high-quality publications by UIRC-affiliated scientists is higher. Since the average number of h index of UIRC group scientists is much higher than that of None-UIRC group scientists, reflecting that the long-term impact of papers referenced is comparable.

Collaborators

In terms of collaborators, this study primarily looked at two indicators—the total number of collaborators and the average number of collaborators per publication—to compare the two groups of scientists. The average number of collaborators per publications in the careers of UIRC group scientists is around 1.8 times higher than that of None-UIRC group scientists ($p < 0.0001$), although the total number of collaborators are roughly equal. This demonstrates that participate in UIRC have a certain “collaborate spillover” effect, with better output and more collaborators, in some ways increasing the talent resources available to academic and industry sectors.

Besides, we also use Cohen's d to detect the effect size of the effect size of UIRC group scientists to None-UIRC scientists across fields and different indicators, the Cohen's d varies between -0.565 to 1.162, with the overall average number of 0.437, indicates that the UIRC group scientists have a better academic performance than that of None-UIRC group scientists.

Figure 3. The effect size of UIRC scientists to None-UIRC scientists across fields and different indicators. Error bars represent 95% confidence intervals.

Conclusion Remarks

In this paper, we firstly examined the UIRC status of 679 Changjiang scholars in six fields from 1999 to 2017 through bibliometric methods and relevant indicators; secondly, we further analyzed the disciplinary characteristics, gender characteristics and collaborative enterprise characteristics of these outstanding scientists through their personal information and publications information. Finally, we examined the impact of UIRC on scientists' academic performance in three dimensions: productivity, research impact and collaborators, and the impact of UIRC on scientists' academic performance was also measured by the total number of publications, citations per publication, the h-index, the total number of collaborators and the average number of collaborators per publication. The results show that, in general, the academic performance of scientists participating in UIRC is better than that of none, as evidenced by the fact that participation in UIRC brings scientists a higher number of publications, more collaborators, and a longer period of high-cited research outputs. This study has several limitations because it was an exploratory study conducted from the perspective of top scientists on an individual basis. For instance, the study sample's discipline coverage is insufficient, and the sample size is limited. Whether there are such obvious differences and effects in other scientific domains needs to be analyzed more comparatively and carefully in order to provide more useful information and references for the theory, practice and policy formulation of UIRC.

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